

Semiconductor Safety Concepts for the Power Distribution of Automated Driving

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AC	Alternating Current
ASIL	Automotive Safety Integrity Level
CA	Collision Avoidance
DC	Direct Current
DC/DC	Direct Current to Direct Current Converter
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
FIT	Failure in Time
FMEDA	Failure Mode, Effect and Diagnosis Analysis
FTA	Fault Tree Analysis
MOSFET	Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor
MTTF	Mean-Time-To-Failure
PMHF	Probabilistic Metric for random Hardware Faults

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

ABSTRACT

Automated driving is a highly complex idea. It involves mechanics, electronics and chemistry, artificial intelligence, human intelligence and high computational efforts. Apart from those aspects, the automated intelligence is run through electricity. An unintended interrupt can easily lead to a hazard. Therefore, a highly reliable power distribution has to be developed. This work focus on the reliability calculation of such a power distribution concept. It points out what is and will be required in future such that the algorithms for the path planning and control are running in a safe environment according to the ISO 26262 standard.

INTRODUCTION

Automated driving is altering the automotive industry. The typical conventions of interaction in traffic are shifted. Microcontroller based systems take over in situations, which have been handled by humans before. Legal issues may arise at failure. To overcome this burden, safety and reliability are critical topics and need to be addressed. While a lot of effort is put into software algorithms, hardware safety has already been in discussion for modern vehicles for many functions. The ISO standard 26262 was first released in 2011, defining the Automotive Safety Integrity Level in respect to severity of the hazard, exposure to the function and controllability at failure.

In [1] specific functions have been considered regarding their safety level. Drive-by-Wire is a necessary part for a highly automated vehicle. Inputs to braking and steering if mechanical connected might happen. A safe disconnection is required for the automated driving, similar to the Fly-by-Wire. Nevertheless, in comparison to airplanes, land vehicles cannot be as costly and do not have the same space for hardware redundancy available.

HARDWARE REDUNDANCY CONCEPTS

The ISO 26262 specifies failure in time (FIT) rates for functions, which endanger human life. Highly hazardous functions have to reach a target of less than 10 FIT, while 1 FIT = 1 failure in 10^9 hours. The FIT rate for the function is calculated by the failure rate of the sub-elements. Every item in the function

does have a specified empirical reliability value $\lambda(t)$. This value is mostly taken out of [2] or [3]. Using the Siemens Norm 29500, the reference value of a single power MOSFET is 60 FIT. Equation 1 is used to calculate $\lambda(t)$ for the power MOSFET, and the actual failure rate is lowered to roughly 25 FIT, only if the device is properly cooled. As virtual reference temperature, the maximum permissible junction temperature defined by the manufacturer is used. For automotive rated products, this temperature ($\theta_{j,1}$) lies up to 175°C. Due to the thermal resistance, the actual junction temperature will be higher than the case temperature. This is considered in equation 3 used in 2 through 4. If actual junction temperature equals the virtual reference temperature, then $\pi_T = 1$ and the FIT rate to be considered is 60. Field return rates do show smaller numbers than the Siemens Norm, which was revised in 2009.

$$\lambda(t) = \lambda_{ref} \cdot \pi_T = 24.93 \text{ FIT} \quad (1)$$

$$\pi_T = \frac{A \cdot e^{Ea_1 \cdot z} + (1 - A) \cdot e^{Ea_2 \cdot z}}{A \cdot e^{Ea_1 \cdot z_{ref}} + (1 - A) \cdot e^{Ea_2 \cdot z_{ref}}} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} z &= 11605 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_{U,ref}} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right) \\ z_{ref} &= 11605 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{T_{U,ref}} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{U,ref} &= 273 + \theta_{ambient,ref} \quad \text{in K} \\ T_1 &= 273 + \theta_{j,1} = 448 \text{ K} \\ T_2 &= 273 + \theta_{j,2} = \theta_{ambient} + R_{th} \cdot P \quad \text{in K} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

A, Ea₁ and Ea₂ are constants

A thorough Fault-Tree-Analysis (FTA) should point at all failures, which can occur. Critical faults should be further assessed within a failure modes, effects and diagnosis analysis (FMEDA). Diagnosis of elements can support the function, such that hazards can be avoided - thereby, lowering the FIT rate for the function. For the diagnosis, the failure modes for the components must be known; depending on the literature, they vary [4, 5, 6]. For the further calculations [4] has been used.

Considering this for a collision avoidance system (CA) (figure 1), which consists of sensors for the environment perception (E1), a microcontroller for computation (E2), a power board for the electronic acutation

(E3) and an electric motor to operate the brakes (E4). The reliability of the overall function is then given by equation 5 for $R(t) = e^{-\lambda t}$, because of the summation of the failure rate (equation 6).

$$R_S(t) = \prod_{i=1}^n R_i(t) \quad (5)$$

$$\lambda_S(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i(t) \quad (6)$$

For specific functions, the target automotive safety integrity level and its FIT rate can be met. Automated vehicles are relying fully on the electric power supply. The drivetrain itself does not have a major influence in the overall safety concept for the power distribution for the automation. A single battery connected to either a DC/DC with an alternator or high voltage battery stack on the other side will not be sufficient. In [7] and [8] the lead acid batteries haven been analyzed. First shows that all batteries have failed after 22 years, and stating 1096 FIT. In the second, a far higher FIT rate - 2057 FIT for the wear out. For all lead acid failure modes, 3414 FIT have been calculated. During automated driving the loss of electric power to control the vehicle is highly hazardous and must be avoided.

In [9, 10] a FIT rate for three phase AC machines was given between 2464 and 22000. The high numbers are mostly driven from bearings and insulation failures. The semiconductors contribute to 5% of the overall rate. However, considering current emission legislations, the alternator will further experience various stress situations. Lastly, the output and efficiency of the alternator is depending on the speed and the load of the system, as pointed out in [11]. Automated driving requires in its current state more power. If the combustion engine is decoupled during sailing the efficiency of the alternator is lowered and the control loop is usually slower than the response of the batteries. Thus, the safety functions will have to rely on the battery.

In [12] the reliability of bidirectional low voltage converters has been assessed. The mean failure in time rate is around 800, while the maximum failure rate is 15% higher. Five out of the seven addressed failure modes can be transferred to a galvanic isolated DC/DC, because they are affecting the semiconductor switches. The latter two are contributing to less than 3% to the overall FIT rate. Thereby it is assumed, that the galvanic isolated DC/DC does have a similar FIT rate.

Supply Source	FIT rate
Battery	1096 - 2057
Alternator	2464 - 22000
DC/DC in combination	800 + secondary supply

Table 2: Supply elements and their FIT rate

Figure 1: An example for collision avoidance

Figure 2: k-out-of-n redundancy

RELIABILITY CALCULATION

The supply sources listed in table 2 have a FIT rate, which is on its own far too high for automated driving. The target level of the power distribution function is 10 FIT (ASIL D). Battery management systems and observers can reduce the failure rate of the battery and thereby proposing maintenance dates. An ASIL decomposition is a feasible choice as proposed in [14]. A supply solution with sufficient independence has to be used. Thereby, creating a k-out-of-n redundancy; similar to figure 2.

The reliability for k-out-of-n redundancy elements (non-repairable) can be calculated with the equation 7. This might result in an 1-out-of-2 redundant system seen in equation 8, under the constraint that the redundancy of the elements is equivalent. This can be used if homogenous redundancy is sufficient. If the systems have to be fully redundant, then they might have a different $\lambda(t)$. The system reliability for a 1-out-of-2 element is calculated by equation 9 for $R(t) = e^{-\lambda t}$. Failures in the system can be detected if implemented. It is not possible to repair the system, while driving.

Power distribution is getting more complex and added supply sources are contributing to a complex bridge structure (figure 3). Such could the reliability model for the distribution look like and is based on figure 4

Element	System
$E1, E1'$ and $E1''$	Batteries
$E2$	Generator
$E3$	DC/DC
$E4$	SBD
$E5$ and $E5'$	Safety Load

Table 3: Description of the abstract power distribution figures

from [15]. It is established on the conventional combustion vehicle and includes the generator. Using a higher voltage than 12V is driven by CO2 regulations and DC/DCs will be required to transfer energy to the 12V distribution system. Either isolated for high-voltage or 48V systems or non-isolated for 48V. $E1$ and $E1'$ are independent batteries and $E3$ and $E3'$ are two DC/DC converters. $E5$ and $E5'$ are the redundant lines of the safety critical function (e.g. Steer-by-Wire, Braking, Sensor Fusion unit...). $E4$ is a disconnection device to split up independently the supply lines for $E5$ and $E5'$. This device is either a mechanical switch in form of a relay or a semiconductor switch. Lastly, $E2$ is the alternator of the vehicle. All elements are listed in table 3.

A mechanical switch does have more disadvantages as pointed out in [15] compared to a semiconductor solution. However, the semiconductor switch is not a single one. MOSFETs will be used to reduce the losses of the switch, but they do feature an internal diode connecting always in one direction. A safe disconnection in two ways, to split up two supply sources independently, requires two MOSFETs in anti-series (figure 5) and is further referenced as Safe Battery Disconnect Switch (SBD). Specific switches for the applications are discussed in [16]. Through observation of the MOSFET during operation, a shorted MOSFET can be detected as well as a stuck-open MOSFET. A control sequence is required for this purpose. A drifting MOSFET might still oppose some problems. Through proper diagnostics, the FIT rate can be lowered. Still the device has to work properly if it must because it is a key element. As target functions have been identified the disconnection under the highest ASIL level and the connection lower, if and only if the overall system is similar to figure 4. This constraint eases the development of the switch. A short of two SBD in series requires two broken devices, while a connection requires two working devices. If one of the switches fails at start up of an automated vehicle, only short ranges (depending on the available energy) to the next garage should be possible.

Using the result equation 1 - 24.93 FIT - for the fail-

Figure 3: An example for a power distribution with redundant supply

Figure 5: SBD Switch - simplified circuit

$$R_S = \sum_{i=k}^n \binom{n}{k} R^i (1-R)^{n-i} \quad (7)$$

$$R_S = 2R - R^2 \quad (8)$$

$$R_S = R_1 + R_2 - R_1 R_2 \quad (9)$$

Figure 4: Redundant power distribution concept for automation levels L3 and higher

ure rate of a single MOSFET in a failure mode, effect and diagnosis analysis, and a high diagnostic coverage the overall rate can be lowered. The safety mechanism in place for a residual fault is the switch in series. For a latent fault, the diagnosis of the MOSFET switch to observe a fault of the single SBD is the safety mechanism. Even though the failure rate has been doubled in first place to nearly 50 FIT the probabilistic metric for random hardware failures (PMHF) is lowered below 10 FIT for the MOSFETs. A stuck open connection do not violate any safety goal in this concept, because of the redundant batteries and DC/DCs. Therefore, a multiple point failure in the system might lead to a loss of service of the automated driving function. A single point failure can be mitigated. The system is fault-tolerant for the power distribution. Errors in the control software are neglected.

The lower FIT rates for these elements, collected in table 2, are used to calculate the overall rate of the system (figure 3). $E1$ the battery on the higher voltage and $E2$ the generator can be seen as parallel element $E12$ with $R_{12} = R_1 + R_2 - R_1 R_2$. From this point onwards, the successful path method is being followed (equation 10 and 11) to calculate further the system from figure 7.

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= e'_1 \cap e_5 & P_2 &= e'_1 \cap e_4 \cap e'_5 & P_3 &= e''_1 \cap e'_5 \\ P_4 &= e''_1 \cap e_4 \cap e_5 & P_5 &= e_{12} \cap e_3 \cap e_5 \\ P_6 &= e_{12} \cap e_3 \cap e_4 \cap e_5 & P_7 &= e_{12} \cap e'_3 \cap e'_5 \\ P_8 &= e_{12} \cap e'_3 \cap e_4 \cap e_5 \end{aligned}$$

$$R_{S0} = P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \cup P_4 \cup P_5 \cup P_6 \cup P_7 \cup P_8 \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_S &= R'_1 R_5 + R'_1 R_4 R'_5 + R''_1 R'_5 + R''_1 R_4 R_5 \\ &+ R_{12} R_3 R_5 + R_{12} R_3 R_4 R_5 + R_{12} R'_3 R'_5 \\ &+ R_{12} R'_3 R_4 R_5 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Figure 6: Abstract example of current power distribution architectures

$$\begin{aligned}
R_S = & e^{-(\lambda_{1'} + \lambda_5)t} + e^{-(\lambda_{1'} + \lambda_4 + \lambda_{5'})t} + e^{-(\lambda_{1''} + \lambda_{5'})t} \\
& + e^{-(\lambda_{1''} + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} + e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& + e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} - e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& + e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} + e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& - e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} + e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_{5'})t} \\
& + e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_{5'})t} - e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_{5'})t} \\
& + e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} + e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& - e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_{3'} + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_S = & 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_5)t} + 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& + 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} + 2e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& - 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_5)t} + 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} \\
& + 2e^{-(\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t} - 2e^{-(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5)t}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Assumed that the FIT rate for the batteries and DC/DCs are equivalent $\lambda_1 = \lambda_{1'} = \lambda_{1''}$ and $\lambda_3 = \lambda_{3'}$ equation 12 is simplified to equation 13. By using the previously mentioned FIT rates for the batteries $E1$, the alternator ($E2$), the DC/DCs ($E3$) and the assumed FIT rates for the SBD and the desired function to be maintained, we can calculate the Mean-time-to-failure (MTTF). For the SBD ($E4$) and the desired available redundant function ($E5$) 10 FIT will be used, as worst case.

As reference system has been used the current power distribution system, consisting of an alternator and a single battery. A more detailed figure of the system can be found in [20]. The abstract system for a single function is illustrated in figure 6. In this system, the fuse boxes have not been included. They increase the FIT rate further. The according equation for this example is given in equation 14.

$$R_S = R_{12}R_5 \tag{14}$$

While the FIT rate of a 12V system with an alternator and a single 12V battery is 972, the proposed system without bidirectional DC/DCs is down to 166 FIT. Bidirectional DC/DCs increase the successful path by two ways, thus improving the FIT rate by further 18 points (148 FIT). Those values have been calculated by equation 15. This difference can be seen in figure 8 over time. While a standard vehicle is far lower, the concept is far longer stable. However, after 3 million hours, all three systems are closing in. As mentioned in the introduction, if the whole system inherits the FIT rate of the safety function of automated driving, the target is ≤ 10 FIT.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{MTTF} &= \int_0^{\text{inf}} R_S(t) dt \\
\lambda_{\text{System}} &= \frac{1}{\text{MTTF}}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Reducing the FIT rate for the power distribution even further, is less driven by the bridge $E4$ than by the batteries, alternator and DC/DCs. Intelligent switches inside the battery could increase the reliability if lower voltages are allowed. A 12V Lithium-Iron-Phosphate battery (LiFePo) features usually four cells in series, resulting in 13.2V. If a cell breaks down, this single cell could be eliminated with a matrix switch. The resulting nominal voltage in this case would be 9.9V. Lithium-Cobalt-Oxide nominal voltage of three cells is at 10.8V. Testing procedures such as [21] requires that any electronic device of type A is capable of performing during and after an undervoltage of 6V as designed. Class B might go out of tolerance but should still be working. 9.9V and respectively 10.8V is at the upper end of the undervoltage range. If safety relevant loads are designed such that they can perform at the smaller voltages, the battery can be seen as repairable devices. Including a matrix switch in the battery opens up to other failure modes. A tradeoff has to be found.

Figure 9 shows the dependencies of the battery, alternator and DC/DC. The highest influence on the FIT rate is given from the batteries, followed by the DC/DC as expected due to their appearance. The target FIT rate for figure 7 can still only be achieved if the SBD and the desired function has a FIT rate of 1. This can be achieved through thorough design development. Far more problematic is to lower the FIT rates for the DC/DC converter and the battery. By lowering the FIT rate to 50 or less for conducting, the overall FIT rate for the system reaches the ASIL D target of 10 FIT. DC/DCs and batteries have both to perform more reliable, especially if the alternator is taken out of the concept for a battery electric vehicle.

Figure 7: System for successful path method with unidirectional DC/DCs

Figure 8: Reliability chart of three different concepts

Figure 9: Reliability chart with variation of the FIT rates

DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

A conservative approach on the FIT rate is not bad if human lives are endangered. The references used by the industry could be updated because they are more than 20 years old. Processes for designing and manufacturing of semiconductors have changed over this period. Even though the alternator exhibits the highest FIT rate it is less crucial because since it is in parallel with the batteries. This path is used once in the calculation. Cutting the FIT rate in half lowers the overall FIT rate by 2%. In battery electric vehicles, the alternator is not present. Key foci are the batteries and the DC/DC. A key issue is to achieve at least 50 FIT for the DC/DC and battery unit. This settles the target ASIL rating for conduction to C for the devices. Designing such electronics and chemistry is highly expensive. Semiconductor components with a high reliability are required. This includes apart from the switches, the drivers, sensors and microcontrollers. Furthermore, the software has to be developed accordingly.

Without semiconductor solutions targeting these parts, a safe power distribution for automated driving is not possible. Adding a higher redundancy could be another option but there are other issues, such as space and weight. Finding the sweet spot between additional elements, weight, CO2 emissions, fuel/electricity consumption, is required. Safety should be always the most important part.

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